

EVALUATION OF PACKED CELL VOLUME, MEAN CELL HAEMOGLOBIN AND PROGESTERONE LEVELS DURING MENSTRUATION AMONG FEMALE MEDICAL LABORATORY SCIENCE STUDENTS OF IMO STATE UNIVERSITY OWERRI, NIGERIA.

BY

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ABSTRACT

Background: Menstruation is a cyclical physiological process governed by hormonal fluctuations, particularly estrogen and progesterone, which may influence hematological parameters. Recognizing these variations is important for accurate clinical interpretations of blood test results in reproductive-aged women.

Objective: This study aimed to evaluate the changes in packed cell volume (PCV), mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH), and serum progesterone across different menstrual phases among female Medical Laboratory Science students of Imo State University, Owerri.

Methods: A longitudinal study was carried out among 30 healthy female students aged 18 to 28 years with regular menstrual cycles. Blood samples were collected at three points within the same cycle: during menstruation (days 1–3), follicular phase (days 7–10), and luteal phase (days 21–24). PCV and MCH were measured using an automated hematology analyzer, and serum progesterone levels were determined using ELISA. Data were analyzed using paired t-tests, ANOVA, and Pearson correlation.

Results: PCV showed no statistically significant variation across menstrual phases ($p > 0.05$). MCH was significantly lower during menstruation (22.80 ± 0.99 pg) compared to the follicular (28.13 ± 1.33 pg) and luteal phases (29.47 ± 1.31 pg) ($p < 0.0001$). Progesterone levels were significantly elevated in the luteal phase (14.43 ± 5.08 ng/ml) compared to the menstruation (0.48 ± 0.18 ng/ml) and follicular phases (0.62 ± 0.23 ng/ml) ($p = 0.011$ and $p < 0.001$). A positive correlation was observed between progesterone and PCV during menstruation ($r = 0.45$, $p = 0.011$).

Conclusion:

While PCV remained relatively stable, MCH and progesterone levels varied significantly throughout the menstrual cycle. These findings highlight the importance of considering menstrual phase when interpreting hematological and hormonal results in young women.

Keywords: Menstrual cycle, Packed cell volume, Mean corpuscular hemoglobin, Progesteron.

INTRODUCTION

The menstrual cycle is a naturally occurring, hormone-driven process that prepares the female body for potential pregnancy. It is orchestrated by a delicate interplay of estrogen, progesterone, luteinizing hormone (LH), and follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) (Hall, 2021). These hormonal fluctuations not only govern reproductive events but also influence systemic physiological parameters, including hematological and immune responses (Lockwood, 2011).

During menstruation, blood loss may result in subtle but important hematological changes, especially in packed cell volume (PCV) and red cell indices like mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH) (Greenblatt, 1970). Progesterone, a key hormone in the luteal phase, is known to affect fluid balance, erythropoiesis, and overall metabolic activities (Mikhail, 1994).

This study will improve the understanding of how hematological and hormonal values shift during different menstrual phases. However, data on these cyclic changes among Nigerian females particularly young adults in academic settings are limited. This study investigates the variations in PCV, MCH, and serum progesterone levels during menstruation, the follicular, and luteal phases among healthy female students in Imo State University, Owerri.

METHODOLOGY

Study Area

The research was conducted at the Department of Medical Laboratory Science, Imo State University, Owerri. The city lies in southeastern Nigeria, characterized by a tropical climate with wet and dry seasons.

Study Design

This was a longitudinal observational study designed to track hormonal and hematological changes within a single menstrual cycle. Each participant provided three samples across different phases: menstruation (days 1–3), follicular phase (days 7–10), and luteal phase (days 21–24).

Study Population

Thirty healthy female Medical Laboratory Science undergraduates aged 18–28 years were involved in this study. Inclusion criteria required regular menstrual cycles and absence of chronic illness, hormonal therapy, or blood disorders.

Method of Recruitment

Participants were selected via purposive sampling. After giving informed consent, participants were closely monitored and guided to ensure correct timing of sample collection relative to their menstrual phases.

Ethical Consideration

Approval was obtained from the Ethical Review Committee of Imo State University, Owerri. Participation was voluntary, and data confidentiality was maintained throughout.

Sample Collection

From each participant, 5 ml of venous blood was collected per phase. Two milliliters were dispensed into EDTA tubes for hematological analysis, while the remaining 3 ml were transferred into plain tubes, allowed to clot, and centrifuged for serum extraction for progesterone testing.

Laboratory Procedures

Hematological Analysis: This was performed using a Mindray BC-3000 Plus hematology analyzer to assess PCV and MCH.

Hormonal Assay: Serum progesterone was analyzed using ELISA kits (Monobind Inc., USA), following the manufacturer’s instructions.

Statistical Analysis

All data were analyzed using SPSS version 25.0. Descriptive statistics were calculated as mean ± standard deviation. Comparisons

were made using repeated measures ANOVA and paired t-tests. Pearson correlation was used to evaluate relationships between progesterone and hematological parameters. A p-value < 0.05 was considered significant.

FINDINGS

Findings from this study are presented in the tables below;

As indicated in table 1, there was no significant difference in the mean value of PCV (0.35±0.03) L/L in the students during menstruation when compared to during the follicular phase of their menstrual cycle (0.35±0.02)L/L (t= 0.79 p=0.435).

The mean values of MCH (22.80±0.99) pg and progesterone (0.48±0.18)mg/ml were significantly reduced when compared to the follicular phase of their menstrual cycle [(28.13±1.33)pg and (0.62±0.23)ng/ml]. (t=17.56,p < 0.0001 and t=2.63, p=0.011)

Table 1: Mean Values of PCV, MCH and Progesterone in Female Students during Menstruation Versus Follicular Phases of their Menstrual Cycle

Parameter	Menstruation n=30	Follicular Phase n=30	t-value	p-value
PCV (L/L)	0.35±0.03	0.35±0.02	0.79	0.435
MCH (pg)	22.80±0.99	28.13±1.33	17.56	<0.0001*
Progesterone (ng/ml)	0.48±0.18	0.62±0.23	2.63	0.011*

Key: * = Significant p value; SD = Standard Deviation;PCV= Packed Cell Volume;MCH= Mean Cell Haemoglobin

From table 2, there was no significant difference in the mean value of PCV

0.35±0.03) L/L of the students during menstruation when compared to the luteal

phase of their menstrual cycle (0.36±0.03)L/L (t= 1.42, p=0.160)

The mean values of MCH (22.80±0.99) pg and progesterone (0.48±0.18) ng/ml were significantly reduced in the students during their menstruation and when compared to

the same students when they are in the luteal phase of their menstrual cycle (29.47±1.31) pg and (14.43±5.08) ng/ml respectively (t= 22.233, p < 0.0001 and t= 15.02, p < 0.0001).

Table 2: Mean Values of PCV, MCH and Progesterone during Menstruation and Luteal Phase.

Parameter	Menstruation n=30	Luteal Phase n=30	t-value	p-value
PCV (L/L)	0.35±0.03	0.36±0.03	1.42	0.160
MCH (pg)	22.80±0.99	29.47±1.31	22.23	<0.0001*
Progesterone (ng/ml)	0.48±0.18	14.43±5.08	15.02	<0.0001*

Key

* = Significant p value; SD = Standard Deviation; PCV= Packed cell volume; MCH= mean cell Haemoglobin

There was no significant difference in the mean values of PCV (0.35±0.02)L/L in students during the follicular phase when compared to the luteal phase (0.36±0.03)L/L (t=1.42, p=0.408) as revealed in table 3.

The mean values of MCH (28.13±1.33)pg and progesterone (0.62±0.23)ng/ml were

significantly reduced in students during their follicular phase when compared the luteal phase [(29.47±1.31)pg and (14.43±5.08)ng/ml] respectively (t=22.23, p< 0.0001 and t=15.02, p < 0.0001)

Table 3: Mean Values of PCV, MCH and Progesterone of participants in their Follicular and Luteal Phases

Parameter	Follicular Phase	Luteal Phase	t-value	p-value
PCV (L/L)	0.35±0.02	0.36±0.03	1.42	0.408
MCH (pg)	28.13±1.33	29.47±1.31	22.23	<0.0001*
Progesterone (ng/ml)	0.62±0.23	14.43±5.08	15.02	<0.0001*

Key: * = Significant p value; SD = Standard Deviation; PCV= Packed cell volume; MCH= mean cell Haemoglobin

However, there was a significant progressive increase of MCH from the menstruation period (22.80±0.99)pg to the follicular (28.13±1.33)Pg and luteal (29.47±1.31)pg phases, (t=250.36, p < 0.0001)

As shown in table 4, there was no significant difference in the mean values of PCV in the participants during the menstrual (0.35±0.03)L/L, follicular, (0.35±0.02)L/L and luteal phases (0.36±0.03)L/L (t=1.19, p= 0.307)

Also, there was a significant increase in the mean values of progesterone levels from the menstrual period (0.80±0.18)mg/ml to the follicular (0.62±0.23)mg/ml and luteal phases (14.43±5.08)mg/ml (t=222.93; p < 0.0001)

Table 4: Comparison of the Mean Values of PCV, MCH and Progesterone of Participants during Menstruation. Follicular and Luteal Phase.

Parameter	Menstruation	Follicular Phase	Luteal Phase	f-value	p-value
PCV (L/L)	0.35±0.03	0.35±0.02	0.36±0.03	1.19	0.307
MCH (pg)	22.80±0.99	28.13±1.33	29.47±1.31	250.36	<0.0001*
Progesterone (ng/ml)	0.48±0.18	0.62±0.23	14.43±5.08	222.95	<0.0001*

Key: * = Significant p value; SD = Standard Deviation; PCV= Packed cell volume; MCH= mean cell Haemoglobin

Findings from table 5 showed that there was a significant positive correlation of progesterone with PCV among the students

during menstruation (r=0.45, p=0.011), and a non-significant positive correlation of progesterone with MCH among the students during menstruation (r=0.02, p=0.917).

Table 5: Correlation of Progesterone with PCV and MCV in Menstruating Student of Imo State University

Variable	N	r	p-value
PCV (L/L)	30	0.45	0.011*
MCH (pg)	30	0.02	0.917

Key: * = Significant p value; SD = Standard Deviation; PCV= Packed cell volume; MCH= mean cell Haemoglobin

DISCUSSION

This study evaluated the changes in PCV, MCH, and progesterone levels across the

menstrual cycle in healthy young women. As expected, progesterone levels peaked during the luteal phase, consistent with the hormone's secretion by the corpus luteum post-ovulation (Speroff and Fritz, 2010). Progesterone values during menstruation and follicular phases were significantly lower, which aligns with established physiological patterns (Reed Carr, 2022). Interestingly, MCH showed a significant increase from the menstruation to luteal phase. This could be attributed to compensatory erythropoietic activity following menstrual blood loss as opined by (Adinma, 1990). Lower MCH during menstruation might reflect transient iron depletion or altered hemoglobin synthesis, as suggested in earlier studies of (Kulkarni, 2015). PCV remained stable across the cycle, showing no statistically significant variation. This suggests that the extent of menstrual blood loss in healthy young women may not be enough to cause a notable reduction in PCV, corroborating findings from similar populations (Thomas and Thomas, 2000). A significant positive correlation between progesterone and PCV during menstruation suggests a possible influence of the hormone on erythropoiesis or fluid regulation as averred by (Bernstein et al., 2001).

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that while PCV remains relatively constant, MCH and progesterone levels vary significantly during the menstrual cycle. Clinical interpretation of hematological and hormonal parameters in menstruating women should thus account for the cycle phase to avoid misdiagnosis or unnecessary concern.

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